

The Impact of the Perceived Image of Local Products on Consumers' Attitudes Towards Local Products

Harrasse Oualid¹, Marso Saida²

^{1,2}Université Abdelmalek Essaadi/ ENCG Tanger

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 20 May 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Harrasse Oualid</p>	<p>Local products, distinguished by their particular geographical origin and traditional production techniques, are gaining popularity among consumers. This article focuses on understanding the impact of the Perceived Image of Local Products on consumers' attitudes toward Chefchaouen local products (CTP), with the aim of identifying and understanding the factors influencing their purchase and consumption decisions.</p> <p>From the analysis of the results obtained from the quantitative study, it appears that consumers have, overall, a positive perception of Chefchaouen local products with a strong preference for some of them. These consumers perceive these products as having added value in terms of quality, authenticity and support for the local economy. Also, these results revealed that the Perceived Image of the Local Product has a positive effect on consumer behavior. Indeed, these results also highlight that a positive attitude of consumers towards products significantly influences their purchase intention, which in turn impacts their actual behavior.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Local, local products, Perceived image of the local product, consumer attitude, intention and behaviour.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

The perceived image of Chefchaouen's local products plays a decisive role in shaping consumer attitudes toward them. These products, deeply rooted in the province's cultural traditions and agricultural practices, benefit from a perceived added value.

Chefchaouen local products (CTP) are often perceived as authentic and of high quality. This perception is reinforced by their close connection to the terroir, which gives these products a unique identity. Consumers associate this authenticity with traditional agricultural practices and local know-how, which positively influences their purchasing attitudes and behaviors.

The perceived image of local products not only influences consumer attitudes; it also affects their purchasing decisions. Consumers are more likely to purchase products they perceive as authentic and of high quality. This perception can also strengthen their loyalty and commitment to them.

Studying the role of the perceived image of local products offers a promising avenue of research. It provides a better understanding of how this image influences consumer attitudes and behaviors. For marketing managers, this understanding is essential for developing effective strategies that reinforce the perceived value of products and create lasting relationships with consumers.

The main interest of this study for Chefchaouen's local products is that it allows us to determine the weight of intrinsic and extrinsic factors on which consumers base their choice of a local product. Understanding the mechanisms behind the purchasing behavior of local products becomes fundamental to developing and deploying an appropriate marketing concept. In addition, it can help local economic development and measure consumer interest in characteristics that could be associated with experiential dimensions such as communication value or sharing value.

II. THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This section outlines the key concepts of our research and the relationships between them. This framework aims to provide a clear and coherent vision of the research objectives, while establishing a solid basis for defining the scope of investigation.

A. Local Products

1) **Definitions:** For decades, local products have been highly prized and continue to grow in popularity. However, their definition remains vague and varies across disciplines and authors, creating a situation of polysemy. This diversity of definitions is influenced by individual perceptions and is evident even within the same discipline.

The literature review reveals that the term "local products" has its origins in the French Revolution, although its history is difficult to trace [15]. The term, as it is used today in some French-speaking countries, does not exist elsewhere. For example, Italians speak of "prodotti tipici" or "nostri," while the Spanish use "productos de la tierra" [15].

In the collective imagination, local products are perceived as natural and authentic, their identity closely linked to their geographical origin. This identity is based on specific physical and cultural elements, reinforced by the fact that they are produced in regions where natural conditions and traditional know-how are passed down from generation to generation.

The literature review reveals that terroir products are generally described as locally produced products, where the interaction between humans and nature shapes their characteristics. They embody the identity of the terroir to which they are linked, associated with a specific territory, natural heritage, traditions, and history.

The first studies on these products, initiated by geographers, aimed to establish links between their characteristics and their places of production. Other disciplines, such as sociology, ethnology and agronomy, then explored their construction and impact [12] [14] [24].

The production of local products is often traditional, but new methods are emerging. Ricard defines them as "products that are characterized by a real originality linked to the local environment including the physical characteristics of the terroir and significant manufacturing constraints. The product is specific to the geographical area from which it originates and it seems impossible for those from other regions to manufacture exactly the same product" [41].

According to Lagrange and Trognon, these products "include any food product, processed or not, bearing a quality mark or not, having a tangible link with the local area or not, having a geographical identity or not, being recent or old, which benefits from a local image among consumers, through its name and the communication which supports its marketing" [31]

Bérard and Marchenay emphasize shared knowledge and practices, anchored in a place and a history and strongly influenced by cultural and environmental factors, they define them as being "local products cross space, time and are based on shared knowledge and practices, they are located in a place and have a history. In other words, these products are more or less markedly part of a culture" [14].

Belletti and Marescotti point out that "a local product can be associated with territorial production and processing conditions based on specific local resources, including social, cultural and environmental ones." [11]

In order to synthesize the definitions mentioned above, with regard to the recognition of local products as such, we can formulate the following ideas which, far from being mutually exclusive, complement each other:

– A local product is an agri-food product, whether in its raw or processed state.

– The characteristics and specificities of a local product are the result of the interaction between this product and its environment, whether raw or processed.

– A local product must be confined to a geographical area that gives it the opportunity to distinguish itself from other products.

– The know-how of the community, particularly the producers established in the territory of origin, constitutes a determining factor in the existence of this local product. This know-how is the manifestation of a subtle adaptation of this community to its environment.

– Time is also a factor that must be taken into account, which determines the anchoring of this product in the history of a territory.

– The recognition of a local product can be based on the identification of the physical environment and the actors who make its existence real.

2) The links between local products and the land are both physical and cultural: Humans play a crucial role in structuring their geographical space, influencing their perception and sense of belonging. Natural factors, such as soil and climate, create an initial connection between local products and their local environment, contributing to their uniqueness [7].

The link between a local product and its environment is a reality, manifested by unique physical and sensory characteristics. This link makes it possible to produce products that cannot be reproduced elsewhere. It is also mutual because these local products offer the region additional competitiveness compared to other regions, thus fully contributing to a genuine territorial dynamic [41].

The originality of local products lies in their local roots, their heritage dimension, and the promotion methods developed by local stakeholders. However, beyond the physical connection, other factors, such as production techniques and methods, also play a crucial role in the production and final characteristics of the products.

The relationship between local products and their territory is both material and cultural. A terroir is a geographical area where traditional know-how and local customs are used to produce local products. These products reflect local methods, techniques, and skills, giving them a uniqueness that embodies the social and cultural aspect of the terroir. According to L. Bérard and P. Marchenay, "Promoting products from our terroirs also means highlighting our know-how and the riches that embody our traditions and culture" [14].

Local products symbolize cultural diversity, and their promotion highlights local know-how and traditions. According to [19], the link between local products and a territory has a dual meaning. It is characterized not only by "physical, geological, or pedoclimatic elements, but also by the fruit of a social and heritage construction." According to Barjolle and colleagues, expertise is crucial for understanding the link between a product, its terroir, and its past. This specific knowledge meets cultural and innate requirements.

Know-how is essential for understanding the link between a product and its terroir and its history. This specific knowledge meets cultural and natural needs [7].

The growing interest in these skills stems from the recognition of their benefits, such as soil protection, ensuring local food supply, water management, crop diversification, innovation, and the preservation of rural jobs. In short, know-how is the result of an accumulation of collective experiences, embedded in a historical and cultural process, and constitutes a collective heritage.

B. The Perceived Image Of The Local Product

People consume local products because they see certain types of value and a perceived image that are specific to them. In this section, we provide some clarifications about this construct.

Research on the Perceived Image of Local Products (PILP) has highlighted that it is a multidimensional concept and incorporates several interconnected aspects. These dimensions include Geographic Origin, Collective Know-How, and Historical Anchoring. Each facet contributes to the formation of a comprehensive and coherent image of the local product, thus influencing consumers' perceptions and attitudes toward these products.

– Geographical Origin (GEO) is a fundamental component of the Perceived Image of Terroir Products. It refers to the specific geographical location where terroir products originate. This geographical origin is often associated with unique characteristics of the soil, climate, and local agricultural practices. Consumers associate these products with superior quality and particular authenticity, which reinforces their positive perception of the terroir product. Studies have shown that geographical origin is a determining factor in the purchasing decision for terroir products, thus validating this hypothesis.

– Collective Know-How (CKH) is another crucial component of the Perceived Image of Local Products. It encompasses artisanal skills, traditional techniques, and local know-how used in the production of local products. Consumers value products made with traditional methods and specific skills because they perceive these products as high-quality and authentic. Collective know-how is therefore a key element that contributes to the positive perception of local products. Research has confirmed that traditional know-how is an important factor in the valuation of local products, validating this hypothesis.

– Historical Anchorage (HAN) is a temporal dimension of the Perceived Image of the Local Product. It includes the history and tradition associated with local products. Products with a long history and well-established traditions are often perceived as having added value. This positive perception of historical anchorage strengthens consumers' purchasing attitude, as they associate these products with continuity and historical authenticity. Studies have shown that the temporal dimension is an important factor in the perception of local products, validating this hypothesis.

In the literature, this construct represents a consumer's perception of local products. According to research, it has an influence on consumer purchasing behavior. The latter builds the perceived image of the local product through the terroir, which for them represents the reflection of the product's quality while allowing them to be an actor in their choices with a view to seeking rewarding experiences. This is confirmed by numerous research work such as that of Aurier and Fort (2004) on the effect of the geographical origin of the local product on the evaluation of consumers and those d'Ambrosini et al. (2008) on consumers' perception of mountain food products. For these consumers, these dimensions feed their beliefs in terms of a guarantee of authenticity and evoking the past and therefore security since it has stood the test of time and has therefore proven itself [13]. They also arouse in them a certain nostalgia which benefits the image of the local product and contributes to the expression of social bonds and the feeling of belonging.

C. The Attitude

1) Definitions: Research on the concept of attitude began in the 1920s, when researchers attempted to determine the elements that influence the link between the perception of stimuli and actual behavior [45]. Attitude models from this period aimed to explain orientations toward an object or action [22]. A review of the literature indicates that definitions of the term 'attitude' can be grouped into two schools of thought: the first associates attitude with behavior, while the second emphasizes its evaluative function.

Authors belonging to the first school define attitude by its influence on behavior. Among them, we can cite:

– Allport defines attitude as "a state of moral readiness [...] exerting a dynamic influence which directs an individual's response" [2].

– Doob defines it as "an implicit response which [...] influences subsequent responses." [21]

– Campbell (1963) for his part, makes attitude a cornerstone in his definition by saying that it is "[a] learned disposition towards a behavior".

These definitions have in common that they consider attitude as a decisive element in the outcome of behaviors. It is also considered as an intermediate variable that directs action towards a material object, an individual or an abstract entity.

Previous definitions establish a direct link between attitude and behavior. However, some researchers of the second school believe that this relationship is fragile and unstable [49]. They consider re-evaluating attitude by taking into account other factors, such as intrinsic characteristics. From this perspective, attitude is considered a summary of the consumer's beliefs, resulting from an assessment.

A first definition suggests that "attitude towards a brand is defined as the degree of satisfaction of his needs that the consumer considers that this brand can bring him." [27].

Another describes it as "the consumer's evaluation of the ability of different brands or products to satisfy their needs." [3].

Although these definitions show that this second stream is more suitable for conceptualizing attitude, it is important to broaden their scope to encompass not only objects, but also actions.

2) The dimensionality of attitude: The multidimensional aspect of attitude refers to the different components or dimensions that constitute an attitude. These dimensions include various elements influencing how an individual perceives and reacts to an object. There are two distinct approaches to conceptualizing attitude: the unidimensional approach and the multidimensional approach.

In the first approach, attitude is considered a holistic notion translating a positive or negative reaction towards an act or an object, judged to be unidimensional and focused on the emotional aspect [6] [7] [43]. Many studies have attempted to decipher a person's attitude towards an object, based on beliefs related to its characteristics, in accordance with the multi-attribute linear compensatory model [1] [50]. Although this model has been commonly adopted as a paradigm [5], it has been questioned regarding the meaning of its terms and their explanatory power [50].

According to the second approach, attitude is perceived as a tendency resulting from two or three elements [25] [30] [38] [29] [42] [44]. It integrates a cognitive dimension, which denotes non-evaluative beliefs about an object, an affective dimension illustrating emotional reactions of attraction or rejection to this object, and a conative dimension, associated with actions and behavioral intentions. The multidimensional aspect of attitude raises questions concerning the relationship between these dimensions.

According to [32], the cognitive dimension precedes the affective dimension, which in turn leads to the conative dimension, while [39] argues that the sequence of these dimensions can change. Researchers such as [8] and [9] [10] propose a two-dimensional model of attitude: hedonic, related to the consumer's affective reward, and utilitarian, referring to the practical characteristics of an object [35] [46].

3) Link between attitude and behavior: According to some authors, understanding a person's attitude could facilitate the prediction of their behavior. However, attitude is not the only factor that influences behavior; the current situation also plays a role [36]. Research on the relationship between behavior and attitude, which began in the 1960s, frequently disappointed researchers by demonstrating the fragility of this link. It was only in the mid-1970s that the crucial role of attitudes in influencing behavior was reiterated.

However, it has been revealed that attitudes are not the only elements influencing behavior, and that contextual factors also have an impact. Several models, incorporating different independent variables, have been developed to clarify this relationship. The theory of reasoned action [23],

supported by a multitude of empirical studies, remains an important framework for anticipating attitude-based behavior.

III. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The hypotheses of our research concern those which concern the components of the Perceived Image of the Local Product (PILP) and those concerning the effect of this construct on consumer attitudes. They are presented in the following tables.

A. Hypotheses Relating To The Components Of The Perceived Image Of The Local Product (PILP)

The Perceived Image of Local Products (PILP) is a construct that encompasses various aspects related to consumers' perception of local products. This Perceived Image is composed of three main facets: Geographic Origin (GEO), Collective Know-How (CKH), and Historical Anchoring (HAN). Each of these components plays a crucial role in shaping the PILP and influences how consumers perceive and value these products. The PILP is often associated with specific characteristics such as quality, authenticity, and cultural traditions. It grants consumers a key position by changing their attitude and further influences their purchase intentions.

Research has highlighted the importance of the Perceived Image of the Local Product and its significant effect on consumer evaluation. This image plays the role of instigator by providing clarifications used by the consumer to infer beliefs about the quality of the local product. The influence of this image on a consumer's evaluation and the decision to purchase a local product depends on several criteria such as motivation, involvement, ease of finding information about the targeted product, etc.

The following table presents the hypotheses relating to the components of the Perceived Image Local Product.

Table I: HYPOTHESES RELATING TO THE COMPONENTS OF THE PERCEIVED IMAGE LOCAL PRODUCT (PILP)

H _{CPILP}	The Perceived Image Local Product (PILP) is made up of three components: GEO, CKH and HAN
H _{GEO}	The Geographical Origin (GEO) is a component of Perceived Image of Local Products (PILP)
H _{CKH}	The Collective Know-How (CKH) is a component of The Perceived Image of Local Products (PILP)
H _{HAN}	Historical Anchoring (HAN) is a component of Perceived Image of Local Products (PILP)

B. Hypotheses Relating To The Effects Of The Perceived Image Of The Local Product (PILP) On The CTP Purchasing Attitude (ATT)

The Perceived Image of the Local Product (PILP) plays a crucial role in shaping consumer' purchasing attitudes. Chefchaouen Local Products (CTP) are often associated with

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specific characteristics that positively influence consumer perceptions and behaviors. A positive local product image can favorably influence consumer purchasing attitudes. Consumers are more likely to purchase certified local products if they perceive these products as high-quality, authentic, and beneficial to their health and well-being.

The hypotheses (Table II) relating to the effects of the Perceived Image of the Local Product (PILP) highlight the importance of the perceived image of the local product in shaping consumers' purchasing attitude. By understanding and managing the components of this image, such as geographical origin, collective know-how, and historical anchoring, it is possible to strengthen consumers' purchasing attitude and improve the perception of their products.

Table II: HYPOTHESES RELATING TO THE EFFECT OF THE PERCEIVED IMAGE OF THE PRODUCT OF TERROIR (PILP) ON THE PURCHASING ATTITUDE OF CTP (ATT)

H _{PA}	The Perceived Image of the Local Products (PILP) has a positive effect on CTP Buying Attitude (ATT)
H _{PA1}	The Geographic Origin component (GEO) of the Perceived Image of the Local Product has a positive effect on the CTP Purchasing Attitude (ATT)
H _{PA2}	The Collective Know-How (CKH) component of the Perceived Image of the Local Product has a positive effect on the CTP Purchasing Attitude (ATT)
H _{PA3}	The Historical Anchoring component (HAN) of the Perceived Image of the Local Product has a positive effect on the CTP Purchasing Attitude (ATT)

In order to test the validity of these hypotheses, we conducted an empirical study, the methodology of which we will now present.

IV. THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research methodology used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data. To test the model and verify the hypotheses presented above, we conducted a quantitative study, which aimed to understand the impact of the Perceived Image of Terroir on the Consumer Attitude of Chefchaouen's local products.

With the aim of working on a population characterized by a diversity of respondents, the collection was carried out on a sample of 297 consumers spread over two different periods and their selection was carried out randomly.

Data were collected through a face-to-face questionnaire, which included 31 questions including three on consumer attitude.

Before the "full-scale" administration of our questionnaire and to ensure its accuracy and avoid design bias, we carried

out the pre-test, which resulted in a slight modification of the structure of the questionnaire.

Data processing, carried out using IBM SPSS V27, involved preliminary processing of the data (missing data, analysis of the normality of the distribution, search for outliers and search for extreme values).

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Profile Sociodemographic And Socio-Professional Of The Sample

1) *The gender of the sample*: The following table is based on data analysis.

Table II: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE SAMPLE

Gender	Number	%
Men	166	56
Women	131	44
Total	297	100

Figure 1: distribution of the sociodemographic profile of the sample

Statistical analysis of the sample reveals that the majority of respondents are men, representing 55.89% of the sample, while women represent 44.11%. This distribution may be important for understanding gender dynamics in the responses to the questions posed in the study.

2) Age groups

The results of the statistical analysis of the data collected during the survey are summarized in the following table.

TABLE III: THE AGE GROUPS OF THE SAMPLE

Age group	Number	%
Between 18 and 30	47	16
Between 31 and 46	103	34
Between 47 and 62	124	42
More than 62	23	8
Total	297	100.

Figure 2: Distribution of age groups of the sample

These results show that the sample is composed of different age groups, with a slight predominance of respondents aged 47 to 62.

3) *The level of study of the sample*

The results concerning the level of study of the sample of respondents are presented in the following table.

TABLE IV: THE LEVEL OF STUDY OF THE SAMPLE

Level of study	Number	%
Primary	9	3.0
Secondary	29	10
Baccalaureate	119	40
License	99	33
Master	38	13
Doctorate	3	1.0
Total	297	100.0

Figure 3: Distribution of the level of study in the sample

The sample is predominantly composed of individuals with higher study, with a high concentration around the bachelor's and bachelor's degrees. This suggests an overall high level of education among participants. Primary and doctoral levels are the least represented, indicating a low proportion of individuals at the extremes of the educational spectrum.

4) *Socio-professional category*: The distribution by socio-professional category of the sample of respondents is presented in the following table.

TABLE V : SOCIO-PROFESSIONAL CATEGORY

Occupation	Numbe	%
Student	17	6%
Employee	76	26%
Retirement	16	5.39%
Worker	49	16.50
Liberal	51	17.17
Official	82	27.61
Looking for a job	6	2.02%
Total	297	100%

Figure 4: Distribution of the socio-professional category of the sample

The sample is primarily composed of employees and civil servants, with a significant representation of the liberal professions and manual workers. Students, retirees, and job seekers constitute smaller proportions. This suggests professional diversity in the sample, with a predominance of active workers, particularly in the public sector.

B. *Attitude Of Respondents*

With a significant percentage (76.8%), the respondents declared that they are willing to buy CTPs if they are offered them.

Table VI : CTP PURCHASE PROVISION

	Number	%
Very willing	177	60
Reluctant	51	17
Not willing	69	23

Figure 5: Distribution of willingness to pay a price surplus for the purchase of CTPs

Most of the respondents (70%) said they are also willing to pay a premium of price for a labeled or marked local product from Chefchaouen.

Table VII : WILLINGNESS TO PAY A PRICE SURPLUS

	Number	%
Yes	207	70%
No	90	30%

Most of the respondents stated that they would be reassured about the quality if they were offered a labeled local product from Chefchaouen.

Table VIII: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS' ATTITUDES REGARDING QUALITY REASSURANCE

	Very reassured		Rather reassured		Not reassured		Rather not reassured		Not at all reassured	
	Nb	%	Nb	%	Nb	%	Nb	%	Nb	%
The label provides sufficient information on the quality of Chefchaouen's local products.	76	25.59	72	24.24	89	29.97	37	12.46	23	7.74
The label highlights the quality of Chefchaouen's local products	81	27.27	75	25.25	83	27.95	35	11.78	23	7.74
The labeling demonstrates compliance with the quality commitments of Chefchaouen's local products.	90	30.30	94	31.65	94	31.65	11	3.70	8	2.69
Labeling reassures consumers about the authenticity and quality of products	82	27.61	86	28.96	97	32.66	16	5.39	16	5.39

Analysis of the data presented in the table above reveals that the majority of respondents are reassured by the impact that labeling can have on the quality of Chefchaouen's local products. However, a minority of respondents who stated that they are not reassured by it.

C. Results of the research hypothesis test

This section presents the testing of the research hypotheses and the analysis of the results obtained in order to confirm or refute them.

1) The results of composition of perceived image of local products: H_{CPILP} ; H_{GEO} ; H_{CKH} ; H_{HAN} hypothesis

The H_{CPILP} hypothesis assumes that the Perceived Image of the Local Product (PILP) is influenced by three facets: Geographic Origin (GEO), Collective Know-How (CKH) and Historical Anchoring (HAN).

The H_{GEO} ; H_{CKH} and H_{HAN} hypotheses postulate that each of these facets contributes partially to the construction of the Perceived Image of the Local Product (PILP).

Table X compiles the results obtained from the test of these variables in the construction of the Perceived Image of the Local Product.

All the H_{CPILP} ; H_{GEO} ; H_{CKH} and H_{HAN} hypotheses concerning the Perceived Image of the Terroir Product are validated. The Perceived Image of the Terroir Product (PILP) is composed of three facets: Geographic Origin (GEO), Collective Know-How(CKH) and Historical Anchoring (HAN)

The results show that all of these variables interact to form the Perceived Image of the Local Product. The model fits the data well, the indices are close to the recommended values (normed $\chi^2 = 2.469$; RMR = 0.07; RMSEA = 0.065; GFI = 0.898; TLI = 0.950; AIC = 595/506). The values after bootstrapping (CI excludes zero) are all significant. The H_{CPILP} hypothesis is validated.

2) Results of the test of the links between the Perceived Image of the Local Product and the Consumer Attitude: H_{PA} Hypothesis

The H_{PA} hypothesis postulates that the Perceived Image of the Local Product (PILP) has a positive effect on the CTP Purchasing Attitude (ATT) (Table XI). The PILP positively and significantly influences the ATT (b=0.798; p<0.001 with 95% CI [.752; .931] after bootstrap).

TABLE IX: VALIDATION OF H_{CPILP} ; H_{GEO} ; H_{CKH} AND H_{HAN} HYPOTHESES

Assumptions	Before bootstrap			After bootstrap				Validatio
	C sdt β	T	P	μ of β	Inf.	Sup.	P	
H_{CPILP}	0.794	12,518	,000	0.791	[,753	,892]	0.001	Validated
H_{GEO} : GEO \rightarrow PILP	0.995	13,552	,000	0.993	[,931	,999]	0.002	Validated
H_{CKH} : CKH \rightarrow PILP	0.834	12,198	,000	0.831	[,768	,898]	0.001	Validated
H_{HAN} : HAN \rightarrow PILP	0.480	7,802	,000	0.476	[,378	,573]	0.002	Validated

Table X: VALIDATION OF THE H_{PA} HYPOTHESIS

Dependent variable: ATT	Before bootstrap			Before bootstrap				Validatio
	C sdt β	T	P	μ of β	Inf.	Sup.	P	
H_{PA} : PILP	0.826	8,257	,001	0.798	[,752	,931]	0.001	Validate

The results presented in Table X clearly indicate that the three components of the PILP have a positive and significant influence on the dependent variable ATT (p<0.05).

Table XI: INFLUENCE OF PLIP COMPONENTS ON ATT

Dependent Variable:	B	Sdt error	β Sdt	T	P	Relative R ²	Adjusted
H _{PA1} : GEO →ATT	0.735	0.031	0.782	12,53	,000	45.7%	37.5%
H _{PA2} : CKH →ATT	0.648	0.028	0.698	12,95	,000	39.5%	
H _{PA3} : HAN →ATT	0.729	0.032	0.786	13,32	,000	38.4%	

The results in the table above illustrate that the independent variables (components) of the IPPT have an influence on the dependent variable ATT. The highest explanatory value is attributable to the geographical origin component (the relative variance share = 45.7%). The hypothesis H_{PA} is validated.

VI. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

CTPs, with their authenticity, quality, and roots in local traditions, are attracting growing interest among consumers. These products, often perceived as cultural treasures, are valued for their unique taste, traditional production methods, and connection to local heritage. Respondents' attitudes toward these products are influenced by various factors, including perceptions of quality, authenticity, labeling, and price. Understanding these attitudes is essential for any product development operation. Statistical analysis of the collected data yields the following results:

A. CTP Purchase Arrangements

The majority of respondents (76.8%) are willing to purchase the products, while 23.2% are not. This indicates an overall positive disposition to purchase among the respondents. This majority disposition to purchase suggests that the products in question are perceived favorably by a large proportion of the respondents, which could be an indicator of potential commercial success for these products.

B. Willingness to pay extra for labeled CTPs

The majority of respondents (70%) agree to pay a price premium for a labeled CTP, while 30% disagree. This indicates an overall positive willingness to pay more for quality or labeled CTP among respondents. This majority willingness to pay a price premium suggests that respondents value labeled CTP and are willing to pay more for these products, which could be an indicator of commercial success for higher quality or labeled products.

C. Perception of CTP labeling

The responses show a diversity of opinions regarding the labeling of CTPs. Although 49.8% of respondents are very or somewhat reassured by the labeling, a significant proportion (30.0%) are not very reassured, and 20.2% are 'rather not reassured' or 'not at all reassured'. This indicates a mixed perception of the labeling, with a relative majority (50.2%) expressing some dissatisfaction or reluctance regarding the information provided on product quality.

D. Perception of the label in terms of authenticity and quality

The responses show a diversity of opinions regarding the labeling of CTPs in terms of authenticity and quality.

Although 56.6% of respondents are very or somewhat reassured by the labeling, a significant proportion (32.7%) are not very reassured, and 10.8% are 'rather not reassured' or 'not at all reassured'. This indicates a mixed perception of the labeling, with a relative majority (43.5%) expressing some dissatisfaction or reluctance regarding the authenticity and quality of CTPs.

E. Perceived Image of the Local Product

The results obtained regarding the construct Perceived Image of the Terroir Product indicate that consumers perceive it as a multidimensional concept that encompasses different facets related to the perception and appreciation of local products. This concept encompasses geographical origin, collective know-how and historical roots.

1) Geographical origin

The majority of respondents (58.2%) consider the geographical origin of CTPs as very important or fairly important. Approximately 23.2% of respondents considered it to be of little importance, while a minority (18.5%) considered it to be not important or unimportant.

The Geographical Origin (GEO) constitutes a key factor in the perception of terroir and local products. It refers to the precise geographical position from which local products originate. It associates this geographical location with the specific characteristics of the soil, the climate and local farming methods. Consumers of CTPs associate them with superior quality and a specific authenticity, which consolidates their favorable image of the terroir.

These results suggest a positive perception of the importance of geographical origin of CTP products among respondents. This could indicate that it is a key factor in the decision to purchase these products, which could have a positive effect on the attitude of respondents.

2) Collective know-how

The majority of respondents (62.6%) consider know-how to be very important or fairly important in CTP. Approximately 21.2% of respondents consider it to be of little importance, while a minority (16.2%) consider it to be not important or unimportant. For these respondents, Collective Know-How (CKH) is seen as a guarantee of quality and authenticity. They know that behind every local product lies a story of passion, dedication, and respect for traditions. This collective dimension strengthens the sense of belonging and local pride. Respondents appreciate the fact that these products are not simply commodities, but living testaments to a cultural and artisanal heritage.

These results suggest a positive perception of the importance of know-how in CTPs among respondents. This could indicate that know-how is a key factor in the decision to

purchase these products, which could have a positive effect on the respondents' attitude.

3) *Historical anchoring*

The majority of respondents (64.7%) are convinced that CTPs refer to local history. Only a minority (24.9%) do not perceive CTPs as being strongly associated with local history. For these respondents, Historical Anchorage (HAN) refers to the roots of local products in the past of the province of Chefchaouen. For them, HAN is an essential element that enriches the consumer experience. They perceive these products as tangible links to the past, products that tell stories and narratives. This historical dimension adds symbolic and emotional value to the products, making them even more precious in the eyes of CTP consumers.

These results suggest a positive perception of the association between CTPs and local history among the respondents. This could indicate a positive experience of the respondents regarding the authenticity and historical value of CTPs, which could have a positive effect on the respondents' attitudes.

F. Effect of Perceived Image of Local Product on consumer attitude

The perceived image of local products plays a crucial role in shaping consumers' purchasing attitudes. A positive image of local products significantly increases consumers' purchasing attitudes. This relationship is robust and statistically significant, even after applying bootstrapping techniques.

VII. CONCLUSION

This research aimed to demonstrate the impact of the perceived image of local products on the attitude of CTP consumers. The results show that the perceived image of local products has a positive effect on the purchasing attitude of CTP consumers. In addition, all of its components also have positive effects on the purchasing attitude of CTP:

– The geographical origin component: this component of the Perceived Image of the Terroir product has a positive effect on the purchasing attitude of CTPs. This means that consumers are more inclined to purchase CTPs when they perceive that these products come from the province of Chefchaouen, which for them remains specific and authentic.

– The historical anchoring component of the Perceived Image of Local Products has a positive effect on the purchasing attitude of CTPs. This shows that consumers appreciate products with a history and tradition, which strengthens their purchasing attitude.

– The collective know-how component has a positive effect on CTP purchasing attitude. This means that consumers are more likely to purchase CTP when they perceive that these products are rooted in a local and authentic culture. This indicates that consumers value the know-how and skills associated with CTP production, which positively influences their purchasing attitude.

The formulated hypotheses were validated, confirming that the components of the Perceived Image of the Local Product (GEO, CKH, HAN) play a significant role in the perception of local products and positively influence the purchasing attitude of CTP consumers.

These results suggest that the perceived image of local products plays a crucial role in shaping consumer attitudes toward CTPs. CTP marketers can leverage these insights to develop marketing and communication strategies. By highlighting the geographical, historical, cultural, and temporal aspects of local products, as well as collective know-how, as differentiating criteria and levers for action, they can positively influence consumer attitudes and, consequently, their purchasing decisions. Effective communication and highlighting these aspects can further amplify this impact, making CTPs preferred choices for consumers concerned about quality, tradition, and responsibility.

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